

8T – Invariance

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Abstract:

By analyzing the framework of the 8T we can analyze one of the most emphasized topics in modern physics which is Gauge invariance, i.e. the fact that the rules of physics are not dependent upon frames of reference. Author will try to reason for it using the main equation and the coupling constant primordial equation, without directly relying upon the gauge theory.

Introduction

By the main equation (1) to (1.2) there is no indication upon frames of reference. The rule of frame of reference can be described using the term of arbitrary variations vanishing into matter, δg_i , in equation (1) as was proven in the thesis.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Suppose that a cluster of arbitrary variation, or fermions is trying to measure a certain particle trajectory, by the first equation he will cause the matrix to accelerate outward in a way that is unique to its arbitrary amount of fermions which he is composed of. Assuming the speed of propagation is the same for all bosonic fields given by the similar structure of the primordial coupling series, the amount of time needed to reach each observer is than different. That was mentioned in the thesis. Now, another point of invariance, is the fact that observers will measure the same magnitudes themselves across the matrix tensor. The coupling constants series is invariant to all, both to matrix tensor coordinate and to the arrow of time.

The reason it is invariant is because the prime ring is invariant, its constant both in location and in time. Eventually all intelligent civilizations will find that the same magnitudes are related to prime numbers and to net curvatures on the matric tensor. The rules are time invariant in that sense as well. They are also manifold invariant, if the prime ring is isomorphic to itself. All universes obey the same rules. To assume nature "invents" new set of rules to each manifold in the manifold packet is not reasonable and does not make sense, if we assume nature inner simplicity.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \quad (2.12)$$

In QFT, we make the subject of invariance by ensuring that the phases will be independent from the amplitudes. Those two observers will measure different angles of the same thing, which is of course briefly stated here. We can state that in the 8T the analog is that in measurement the matric tensor is varying in different amounts, leading to different measurement. That is one way to reason invariance. Regarding measurement of bosons, that is the second way to reason for invariance is to state the following, regarding bosonic measurement – the primes are isomorphic to themselves and according to the coupling series, the propagation process is completely independent of any observer. It will happen, and it will take exactly the same form $2N + 1$ as presented in equations (3) to (3.3). in equation (3) we decomposed the net curvature into two halves, in the rest we used the prime critical line, located on one half.

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow \left[2N_0 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_0 + 1 \quad (3)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (3.1)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (3.2)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (3.3)$$

The analog to QFT is that each observer will observe the curvature vortex is different stages. The curvature vortex is the same for all, but the observation of it will differ, the curvature vortex invariance can be described to chiro-pyramidal groups, which resemble curvature spikes roughly. In the context of bosonic invariance the amount of discrete prime number curvature is independent of any observer, or any fermion cluster. It is matric tensor invariant, temporal invariant and manifold invariant. In other modern theories of physics, the description of invariance is rather technical and involves four vectors and in certain cases several indices. Such methods are not very sufficient as the author believes as they are not getting to the real point of invariance, but that is a topic for another paper.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "8T- Curvature Spikes" In: (2021)